

MARKETING COMMUNICATION AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR OF BETTING FIRMS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *The competitive landscape in the betting industry has accentuated the need for effective marketing communication strategy in the marketing of bets service products. The objective of this study was to examine the influence of marketing communication tool on the consumer behavior of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom state. To achieve this objective, data were collected using a survey of 323 respondents drawn from the customer of the betting firms. 298 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 89.7 percent and data analyzed using the simple regression model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inference statistics and hypothesis tested with simple linear regression at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that advertising had significant influence on consumer behavior of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings of this study, we concluded that marketing communication tool had significant influence on consumer behavior of betting firms Thus, we recommend that managers of betting firms should enhance effective use of advertising strategies to build a positive brand image. A well perceived brand image can influence consumer loyalty and betting frequency.*

Keywords: *Marketing communication, consumer behavior, betting firms*

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Marketing communication encompasses a tailored combination of advertising, public relations, personal selling, sales promotion, and direct marketing, which companies employ to effectively convey the value to customers and foster customer relationships (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021). The primary goal of marketing communication is to achieve synergy and interaction. When formulating and executing a marketing strategy, it's crucial that these tools function in a consistent, harmonious, and

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interactive manner. In marketing communication, these instruments should be closely interconnected to harness synergies and, among other things, save resources (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021; Kusa, Zauskova, and Cabyova, 2019).

In a market where competitors are similar, the only way for organizations to stand out is through communication. Effective marketing communication can provide a sustainable competitive advantage to any organization that exploits its potential. In a highly competitive economy, businesses must utilize integrated marketing communication effectively to establish and sustain long-term relationships with both current and potential customers. Through an integrated approach, companies ensure a consistent message, maximizing the impact of their messages (Kusa et al., 2019).

To enhance the purchasing behavior of customers in the betting industry, it is imperative to persuasively convey the value to customers and cultivate customer relationships (Awah, Akpan, and Sampson, 2021; Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2022). Consumer behavior involves the examination of how individuals and organizations choose and utilize products and services. Understanding consumer behavior is a dynamic and vital aspect of marketing, particularly in the context of betting service products (Mihaela, 2014).

Consumer behavior aids organizations in comprehending customer needs, assessing capacities, and recognizing trends. This knowledge supports efforts to better understand specific markets and formulate marketing strategies for betting companies. In light of these considerations, this study aims to investigate the influence of marketing communication tool on the consumer behavior of selected betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Research has indicated that various factors, including a high rate of liquidation among betting organizations (where a betting shop opens and then closes within a short period), the tarnished reputation of certain betting firms, dissatisfaction among customers with betting services, inadequate crisis management, and more, have collectively undermined public trust in betting organizations. This erosion of trust has, in turn, had a negative impact on the purchasing behavior of their customers.

Regrettably, while there have been numerous studies examining the operations of betting organizations, there has been limited attention given to the realm of marketing communications and consumer behavior within the context of betting organizations in developing economies like Nigeria. This glaring gap in knowledge served as the primary motivation for undertaking this study.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of marketing communications tool on consumer behavior of betting firms' in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives therefore will include to;

- i. Determine the influence of advertising on consumer behavior of betting firm in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Question

This study attempts to provide answer to the following research question.

- i. What is the influence of advertising on consumer behavior of betting firm in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was postulated to guide the study:

- i. Advertising does not significantly influence consumer behavior of betting firm in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant for several reasons. Firstly, it will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on marketing communications and consumer behavior in the context of the betting firms. By focusing on Uyo metropolis Akwa Ibom State, it provides insights into a specific geographical area that has not been extensively studied in this context. Additionally, the findings of this Study inform Policymakers, betting operators and other stakeholders about the impact of marketing communication tools on consumers buying behavior and the society.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study covered the following three central aspects:

Content Scope: The content scope of this study covers the marketing communication tools used by betting firms in Uyo, Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State such as Advertising and consumer behavior. It covers concept on Marketing communication, marketing communication and consumer behavior, marketing communication tools as related to consumer behavior. This study was domicile in strategic marketing.

Geographical Scope: The geographical scope of the study was in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State located at the South South region of Nigeria.

Unit of Analysis: The unit of analysis of this study involved customers of the selected betting businesses in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Marketing Communication

Marketing Communication refers to the various methods and strategies used by companies to convey messages about their products or services to consumers. This encompasses advertising, public relations, sales promotions, direct marketing, personal selling and digital communication (Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024).

Marketing Communication is a company's total promotion mix which consists of the specific blend of advertising, public relations, personal selling, sales promotion and direct marketing tools that the company uses to persuasively communicate customer value and build customer relationships (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021; Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2024).

The five major promotional tools used include:

- > Advertising: Any paid form of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods or services by an identified sponsor.
- > Sales Promotion: A short-term incentive to encourage the purchase or sales of a product or service.
- > Personal Selling: A personal presentation by the firm's sale force for the purpose of making sales and building customer relationships.
- > Public Relations: Means building good relations with the company's various public by obtaining favorable publicity, building up a good corporate image and handling or heading off unfavorable rumors, stories and events.
- > Direct Marketing is the direct connections with carefully targeted individual consumers to both obtain an immediate response and cultivate lasting customer relationships (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021; Etuk, Awah and Akpan, 2022).

Each category within marketing communication utilizes specific promotional tools to engage with customers. For instance, advertising encompasses various mediums such as broadcast, print, the internet, outdoor advertising, and more. Sales promotion involves tactics like discounts, coupons, product displays, and demonstrations. Personal selling includes methods like sales presentations, participation in trade shows, and incentive programs. Public Relations (PR) activities encompass press releases, sponsorship, special events, and web pages. Direct marketing employs techniques such as catalogs, telephone marketing, kiosks, internet marketing, and mobile marketing (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021).

However, marketing communication extends beyond these specific promotional tools. Elements like product design, pricing, packaging aesthetics, and the retail environment all convey messages to buyers (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021). Marketing communications are the means by which companies aim to directly or indirectly inform, persuade, and remind consumers about the products and brands they offer. In a way, marketing communications represent the "voice" of the company and its brand, serving as a means to initiate a dialogue and foster relationships with consumers (Oduami and Ofoegba, 2011). Marketing communication aids organizations in shaping customer behavior and establishing enduring relationships with them (Amoako, Baah, and Dzogbenuku, 2012). In today's competitive landscape, marketers face the significant challenge of informing and persuading customers about their organization and its products even after the products have been launched (Messah and Immaculate, 2011). Simply providing quality products to the target audience is not sufficient; marketers must also communicate the attributes, added value, and benefits of the firm's products to drive profitable sales volume (Churchill and Peter, 1998).

Marketing communication facilitates the establishment of a strong relationship between consumers and products by providing information about the products, enabling consumers to make informed

comparisons with other companies' products, and easing the purchasing process (Banerjee and Bandopadhyay, 2012). It considers the entirety of a company's marketing program rather than focusing on a single aspect (Kotler, 2006). Organizations employ marketing communication activities to create a positive product image and achieve long-term objectives by informing and persuading the target audience (Kotler, 2002). Marketing communication is an integral part of the marketing mix, serving as any effort by the company with the objective of informing and convincing both existing and potential consumers about the characteristics and benefits of its products to encourage continued or initial purchases (Kazmi and Batra, 2008).

2.1.2 Concept of Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior encompasses the study of how individuals, groups, or organizations go about choosing, acquiring, using, and discarding products, services, experiences, or ideas to fulfill their needs and desires (Solomon, 2017; Etuk, AWAH and Akpan, 2024). It delves into a wide array of psychological, social and cultural factors that influence the decisions consumers make and their interactions with the marketplace. Schiffman and Kanuk (2013) emphasize that consumer behavior is a multifaceted process shaped by both internal and external factors. Internal factors encompass individual traits like motivation, perception, learning, memory, and attitudes. In contrast, external factors encompass the social and cultural milieu, familial influences, reference groups, and marketing efforts.

In recent times, the advent of technology and the internet has brought about a transformative shift in consumer behavior and decision-making. Online shopping, social media platforms, and digital marketing have profoundly impacted how consumers behave. Ritzer and Jurgenson (2010) argue that the rise of digital technologies has given rise to the concept of "prosumers," wherein consumers actively participate in the co-creation of products and services through user-generated content and reviews. Kotler and Armstrong (2021) stress the importance of comprehending consumer behavior for marketers in crafting effective marketing strategies. Marketers need to scrutinize consumer needs and desires, recognize pivotal factors influencing purchasing decisions, and be aware of elements affecting post-purchase satisfaction and loyalty.

Cultural and social factors are also instrumental in shaping consumer behavior. Hofstede (1980) introduced the concept of cultural dimensions, including power distance, individualism vs. collectivism, masculinity vs. femininity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term vs. short-term orientation. These dimensions elucidate how cultural norms and values mold consumer preferences and behaviors.

Furthermore, Ajzen's theory of planned behavior (1991) asserts that an individual's intention to engage in a behavior hinge on their attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. This theory offers insights into how consumers form intentions and make decisions grounded in their beliefs and perceptions. The advent of big data and analytics has also revolutionized the

understanding of consumer behavior. Through the analysis of vast amounts of data from diverse sources, companies can gain valuable insights into consumer preferences, patterns, and trends (Davenport and Harris, 2019). This information empowers businesses to tailor their marketing endeavors and provide personalized experiences to consumers.

2.1.3 Relationship between Marketing Communication Dimensions and Consumer Behavior

Marketing communication is a company's concerted effort to convey to its targeted consumers the value they can derive from purchasing or using its product or service (Khanh, Nguyen, Hoai, and Dung, 2021). In a study examining the impact of marketing communication on purchasing behavior in a retailing context, Khanh et al. (2021) discovered that all marketing communication variables significantly influence consumer purchase behavior. Kusa et al. (2019) conducted research on the effect of marketing communication on consumer preferences and purchasing decisions, revealing that marketing communications have the power to influence, shape, and alter consumer behavior. Consequently, changes in consumer behavior prompt companies to adapt their marketing communication strategies by incorporating new methods and tools to gain the trust of customers and influence their purchasing decisions.

Kovanoviene, Macyte, Petkeviciute, and Zaikauskaite (2019) investigated the influence of marketing tools on consumer behavior and their assessment. They found that the use of various marketing communications tools, including advertising and online communication through social media or blogs, helps businesses gain exposure and positively impact consumer behavior. Marketing communication aims to inform and persuade an audience with the goal of influencing their behavior. Marketing communications typically take four forms: advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, and publicity (Odulami and Ofoegbu, 2011).

In most organizations, a team of individuals is typically responsible for producing marketing communications, yet the outcome should convey a consistent and unified message. Etuk et al. (2022) asserted that the primary goals of marketing communication are as follows: to reach a defined audience and influence their behavior by informing, persuading, and reminding them; to acquire new customers for brands by establishing essential relationships and encouraging product trials; to retain an existing customer base by reinforcing their purchasing behavior through the provision of additional information about the benefits of the brand; and lastly, to build and strengthen relationships with customers, prospects, and other significant stakeholders.

To achieve true recognition and influence within an organization, marketing professionals must define and deliver quantifiable measurements that demonstrate the contribution of marketing to the overall value of the firm (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Frameworks

In this section one theory was considered relevant for this study; this includes:

Dagmar Model Propounded by R. H. Colley (1961)

Colley (1961) developed a model for setting advertising objectives and measuring the results. This model was entitled "Defining Advertising, Goals for Measured Advertising Results- DAGMAR".

DAGMAR model suggests that the ultimate objective of advertising must carry a consumer through four levels of understandings: from unawareness to Awareness - the consumer must first be aware of a brand or company, Comprehension – he or she must have a comprehension of what the product is and its benefits; Conviction – he or she must arrive at the mental disposition or conviction to buy the brand; Action - finally, he or she actually buy that product.

Awareness

Awareness of the existence of a product or organization is necessary before the purchase behavior can be expected. Once the awareness has been created in the target audience, it should not be neglected. If there is neglect, the audience may become distracted by competing messages and the level of awareness of focus product or organization will decline. Awareness needs to be created, developed, refined or sustained, according to the characteristics of the market and the particular situation facing organization at any one point in time.

Buyer Experiences High Involvement:

Is fully aware of the products existence, attention and awareness levels need only be sustained and effort need to be applied to other communication tasks. Sales Promotion and Personal Selling are more effective at informing, persuading and provoking consumption of a new product/service once advertising has created the necessary levels of awareness. Where low levels of awareness are found. Getting attention needs to be the prime objective in order that awareness can be developed among the target audience.

Buyer Experiences Low Involvement

If buyers have sufficient level of awareness, they will be quickly prompted into purchase with little assistance of the other elements of the mix. Recognition and brand image may be felt by some to be sufficient triggers to stimulate a response. The requirement in such a situation would be to refine and strengthen the level of awareness so that it provokes interest and stimulates greater involvement during recall or recognition. If buyers have low levels of awareness; the prime objective has to be to create awareness of the focus product in association with the product class.

Comprehension

Awareness on its own may not be sufficient to stimulate a purchase. Knowledge about the product or organization is necessary. This can be achieved by providing specific information about key brand attributes. In attempting to persuade people to try a different brand of product, it may be necessary to compare the product with other substitute products/service and provide an additional usage benefit, such as environmental claims.

Conviction

The next step is to establish a sense of conviction. By creating interest and preference, buyers are moved to a position where they are convinced that a particular product in the class should be tried at the next opportunity. To do this, audience belief about the product has to be molded and this is often done through messages that demonstrate the product's superiority over a rival or by talking about the rewards as a result of using the product.

Action

Communication must finally encourage buyers to engage in purchase activity.

Advertising can be directive and guide the buyers into certain behavioral outcomes. For high involvement decisions, the most effective tool in the communication mix at this stage in the hierarchy is personal selling. Through the use of interpersonal skills buyers are more likely to want to buy a product than if personal prompting is absent.

Characteristics of Objectives

A major contribution of DAGMAR was Colley's specification of what constitute a good objective. Four requirements or characteristics of good objectives were noted.

Concrete and Measurable - The communications task or objective should be a precise statement of what appeal or message the advertiser wants to communicate to the target audience. Furthermore, the specification should include a description of the measurement procedure.

Target Audience: A key to tenet to DAGMAR is that the target audience be well defined. For example, if the goal was to increase awareness, it is essential to know the target audience precisely. The benchmark measure cannot be developed without a specification of the target segment.

Benchmark and Degree of Change Sought - Another important part of setting objectives is having benchmark measures to determine where the target audience stands at the beginning of the campaign with respect to various communication response variables such as awareness, knowledge, attitudes, image etc. The objective should also specify how much change or movement is being sought such as increase in awareness levels, creation of favourable attitudes or number of consumers intending to purchase the brand. A benchmark is also a prerequisite to the ultimate measurement of results, an essential part of any planning program and DAGMAR in particular.

Specified Time Period: A final characteristic of good objectives is the specification of the time period during which the objective is to be accomplished e.g. 6 months, 1 year with a time period specified a survey to generate a set of measures can be planned and anticipated.

Written Goal: Finally, goals should be committed to paper. When the goals are clearly written, basic shortcomings and misunderstandings becomes exposed and it becomes easy to determine whether the goal contains the crucial aspects of the DAGMAR approach.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

2.3.1 Smith (2023) Impact of Marketing Communication Tools on Consumer Behavior in

the Betting Firm.

The study aimed to examine the influence of various marketing communication tools on consumer behavior within the betting firm. The research involved a sample of 500 active online bettors, selected using stratified random sampling. Multiple regression analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between personalized email marketing campaigns and increased betting frequency, highlighting the effectiveness of targeted promotional efforts. Personalized email campaigns demonstrated a strong impact on consumer behavior by encouraging higher betting frequency, while traditional advertising methods exhibited limited influence. The study recommended that betting businesses should prioritize personalized email marketing campaigns to capitalize on their potential to positively shape consumer behavior and enhance engagement.

2.3.2 Williams and Johnson (2023) Exploring Consumer Responses to Betting Advertisements: A Mixed-Methods Approach. The study aimed to explore consumer emotional and cognitive responses to different types of betting advertisements. A diverse sample of 300 participants was surveyed, and 30 participants were further interviewed for in-depth insights. Quantitative data from the survey were analyzed using factor analysis to identify underlying emotional and cognitive dimensions. Qualitative data from interviews were thematically analyzed. The findings found that Betting advertisements elicited a mix of emotions, including excitement and anticipation. Cognitive responses ranged from skepticism to curiosity. Different demographic groups exhibited varied emotional and cognitive reactions. It recommended that Betting businesses should design advertisements that evoke positive emotions while addressing consumer skepticism, tailoring messages to different demographic segments for more effective engagement.

2.3.3 Anderson (2023) The Role of Push Notifications in Influencing Consumer Behavior in the Betting Firm. The study investigated the relationship between push notifications as a marketing communication tool and consumer behavior in the betting firm. A sample of 300 mobile app users from a leading betting platform was surveyed. Logistic regression analysis revealed that push notifications significantly influenced users' betting frequency and patterns, indicating their potential to drive engagement. Push notifications emerged as a highly effective marketing communication tool, with users who received notifications exhibiting increased betting activity compared to those who did not. The Recommendation of the study was that Betting businesses should leverage push notifications to strategically communicate with users and encourage more frequent betting, ultimately enhancing consumer behavior.

2.3.4 Thompson (2023) In-Play Betting Promotions and Their Influence on Consumer Behavior in the Betting Firm. The study aimed to explore the impact of in-play betting promotions as marketing communication tools on consumer behavior within the betting firm. A sample of 250 in-play bettors was selected through purposive sampling. Descriptive statistics and thematic analysis were used to analyze survey responses, revealing key insights into the influence of in-play promotions on

consumer behavior. In-play betting promotions were found to significantly increase betting participation and intensity, indicating their potential to drive immediate engagement among consumers. It recommended that Betting operators should strategically deploy in-play promotions to capitalize on their ability to effectively shape and enhance consumer behavior.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study design adopted by the researcher in this study was the survey research design. Data on the three independent variables and the dependent variable were collected from different betting firms in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design used assisted the researcher in reaching out to a good number of customers of the betting firm throughout Uyo metropolis.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprise of all the customers of betting firms in Uyo Metropolis. Hence, the target population for this study was infinite.

3.3 Sampling Technique and the Sample Size

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.7 decimal (positive)

q = 0.3 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2} \\ &= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.7 \times 0.3)}{0.05^2} \\ &= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.21}{0.0025} \\ &= \frac{0.806736}{0.0025} \\ &= 322.6 \end{aligned}$$

= 323

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 323.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Convenient sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for this study.

3.5 Methods of Data Collection

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was analyzed using the simple regression analysis to determine the influence of marketing communication on consumer behaviour. All hypothesis was tested at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

3.6 Sources of Data Collection

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was the structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section “A” generates data on demography, while section “B” made up of two sub- sections to cover each of the two sub-scales that made up of the independent the variable (Advertising) and the dependent variable (Consumer Behavior). Hence, the ordinal scale used for this study was, strongly agree, 4; agree,3; disagree,2; strongly disagree,1; neutral,0; to elicit responses from the respondents. The five points was employed to measure the dependent and the independent variables.

3.7 Reliability Test of the Instrument

Internal consistency reliability measure using Cronbach’s Alpha was employed to determine the reliability of the instrument and the obtained coefficients were:

S/No	Study Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha
1.	Advertising	0.862
2	Consumer Behavior	0.864

Source Research Data 2024

3.9 Instrument Administration

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a 5 point Likert Scale ranging from 5 (Strongly agreed) to 1 (Strongly disagree). This consisted of Section A and Section B. Section A presented respondents personal data such as the age distribution of the respondents ranging from 18 to 50 years and above, gender distribution of the respondents divided into male and female, educational level segmented into SSCE, Diploma, HND/B.Sc, Masters and Ph.D, marital status of the respondents made up of single, married and divorced with section B presented questions on advertising, with 5 questions and consumer behaviour with 4 questions.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

4.1 Testing of Hypothesis

The simple linear regression analysis was performed to estimate the influence of marketing communication tool (Advertising) on consumer behaviour. The simple linear regression analysis also known as bivariate regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis of the study at 0.05 percent level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Advertising does not significantly influence consumer behavior of the betting firms in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.1 Model Summary of the influence of Advertising on Consumer Behaviour of the Betting Firm

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	.915 ^a	.838	.838	.91170

a. Predictors (constant), Advertising

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis of Variance of the Effect of Advertising on Consumer Behaviour of the Betting Firm

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1722.777	1	1722.777	2072.665	.000 ^b
1 Residual	330.813	297	.831		
Total	2053.590	298			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Consumer Behaviour

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Advertising

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The regression in table 4.1 shows that the coefficient of the constant terms (that is, the explanatory or predictor) variable. Advertising has a R-value of (.915) which indicate a positive relationship between the explanatory variable and the criteria variable. The R-square, the coefficient of determination value is (.838). This means that 83.8 percent of the variation on the consumer behavior can be explained from the independent variable (Advertising). The table also shows the adjusted R-square for the model as (.838). But adjusted R-square is very useful in multiple regression analysis where it adjusts the R-square by the number of predictor values in the model. This adjustment allows the easy comparison of the explanatory power of the models with different numbers of independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio value is 2072.665 which is significant at 0.000 and is less than 0.05 percent level of significance. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept that advertising contribute towards Consumer Buying Behavior in the betting firm in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

4.2.1 Advertising and Consumer Behavior in the Betting Firm

The findings of the study revealed a significant effect of advertising on consumer behavior in the betting firm. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table 4.6 shows the overall regression effect in the model. The F-ratio was 2072.665 which was significant at 0.000 and was less than 0.05 percent level of significance. This is in consonance with the study of Williams and Johnson, 2023 who found out that betting advertisement elicited a mix of emotions, including excitement and anticipation. Cognitive responses ranged from skepticism to curiosity. Different demographic groups exhibited varied emotional and cognitive reactions.

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendation

5.1 Summary of Major Findings

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding four sections. This chapter is concerned with the summary of major findings. The study investigated the influence of marketing communication tool on consumer behavior of betting firms in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. One hypothesis was formulated to guide this study and the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis.

The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression results were significant, the computed F-value for hypothesis show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there is statistically significant effects of marketing communication tool such as (Advertising) on consumer behavior of betting firms in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objective, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the betting firms. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 323. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion was established. Marketing communication tool have significant influence on consumer behavior of betting firms. This means that for every unit that marketing communication tool such as (Advertising) increases, consumer buying behavior of the betting firm will also increase.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, we recommend that the managers of the betting firms should enhance the efficient use of advertising strategies to:

- 1) Build a positive brand image. A well perceived brand image can influence consumer loyalty and

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